

crosses were evaluated. We placed 2-g leaf blades from each plant in 10 ml of 1.7% KOH solution according to the method of Sood and Siddiq. Samples

were smelled and evaluated for aroma after 10 min.

F₁ plants from all the reciprocal crosses were nonaromatic, indicating that

a recessive nuclear gene controls aroma in Jin-Long Dao and 80-66. The F₂ plant scent evaluation indicated a 3:1 (non-aroma:aroma) segregation (see table). □

Breeding methods

Heterosis and inbreeding depression in rice

T. Ram, Central Agricultural Research Institute, Port Blair 744101, India

Ten divergent parents—Mahsuri, Adamchini, IET4140, IET7562, Kanakjeera, IR50, IR52, Dhaneswar, Pawanpeer, and TAU18—were crossed in all possible combinations, excluding reciprocals, to study the extent of heterosis, heterobeltiosis, and inbreeding depression for yield and yield components.

Parents and their 45 F₁ and 45 F₂ were grown in a completely randomized block design, with three replications. Plants were spaced at 20 × 15 cm, with one row of 20 plants for parents and F₁ and six rows of 20 plants for F₂. Observations were recorded for 10 randomly selected plants from parents and F₁, and 50 plants from F₂.

The genotypic correlation coefficient indicated that grain yield was positively and significantly correlated with number of effective tillers/plant ($r = 0.38$) and number of grains/panicle ($r = 0.45$). Other characters, such as days to panicle emergence, plant height, panicle length, and 100-grain weight, showed either negative or nonsignificant positive correlations with yield.

The cross combinations exhibiting more than 20% heterobeltiosis for grain yield are in the table. Crosses showing more than 40% heterobeltiosis for grain yield were Kanakjeer/IR50, IR50/Pawanpeer, IET4140/TAU 18, Adamchini/TAU 18, Adamchini/Pawanpeer, Adamchini/IET7562, and Adamchini/IR50. Crosses showing better negative heterobeltiosis for days to panicle emergence were Adamchini/IET7562 and Adamchini/IR50, IET7562/IR52; for plant height, they were Adamchini/IET7562, Adamchini/Pawanpeer, Adamchini/IR50, IET4140/TAU18, and Kanakjeera/IR52.

Only 11 of 54 crosses showed positive significant heterobeltiosis for number of effective tillers/plant. Crosses with appreciable heterobeltiosis were Mahsuri/Kanakjeera, IET4140/IR52, and IR50/Pawanpeer.

The crosses with high heterobeltiosis for grains/panicle were IET4140/TAU 18, IET4140/IR50, IR50/Pawanpeer, IET7562/IR52, IET4140/IR50, IR50/Pawanpeer, IET7562/IR52, and IET7562/TAU18. The crosses Mahsuri/IET4140 and IET7562/IR50 expressed better heterobeltiosis for 100-grain weight.

Out of 45 crosses, 31 showed significant inbreeding depression for plant height, 32 for days to panicle emergence, 41 for panicle length, 42 for tillers/plant, 31 for grains/panicle, 41 for 100-grain weight, and 42 for grain yield. Some crosses had high heterosis with high inbreeding depression, some showed more heterosis and medium inbreeding depression, and some had high heterosis with low inbreeding depression. □

Heterobeltiosis and inbreeding depression for yield and its components in promising hybrids. ^a

Cross	Days to panicle emergence		Plant height (cm)		Effective tillers/plant (no.)		Grains/panicle (no.)		Grain yield/plant	
	HBT (%)	ID (%)	HBT (%)	ID (%)	HBT (%)	ID (%)	HBT (%)	ID (%)	HBT (%)	ID (%)
Mahsuri/IET7562	-14.5**	-6.3**	3.9**	1.0	-9.0	20.2**	-30.7**	30.4**	34.9**	50.8**
Mahsuri/Kanakjeera	0.1	5.4**	3.8**	13.6**	31.6**	41.1**	-36.7**	26.2**	44.7**	61.7**
Mahsuri/Pawanpeer	-4.3**	13.9**	-1.9	-9.8**	11.3**	49.9**	-36.8**	35.5**	34.3**	56.6**
Mahsuri/TAU18	-7.0**	-2.8*	-2.1	8.8**	-6.5	23.0**	-19.9**	32.8**	20.7**	38.3**
Adamchini/IET7562	-24.6**	-11.9**	-27.7**	-9.2**	-19.0**	32.6**	14.9**	34.0**	54.6**	55.5**
Adamchini/IR50	-17.3**	4.7**	-13.6**	4.4**	-9.3	0.4	-11.2**	2.1	45.0**	22.2**
Adamchini/Pawanpeer	-10.5**	5.7**	-22.7**	15.3**	0.2	18.3**	-40.0**	9.1**	57.4**	17.6**
Adamchini/TAU18	-6.9**	5.3**	7.6**	7.4**	13.4**	26.8**	-9.2**	6.9**	57.5**	28.4**
IET4140/Kanakjeera	-0.1	3.1	-12.9**	9.1**	-5.6	17.1**	38.2**	-52.4**	28.4**	20.9**
IET4140/IR50	4.0**	11.5**	-2.8*	-30.3**	-42.3**	0.5	46.0**	11.3**	41.7**	13.3**
IET4140/IR52	14.1**	5.0**	1.4	10.0**	33.1**	11.1**	-6.4**	8.4**	20.7**	39.7**
IET4140/Pawanpeer	-0.2	2.4*	2.7	12.2**	12.5**	26.1**	14.9**	4.1*	20.4**	15.0**
IET4140/TAU18	0.8	1.4	-15.5**	2.6	2.7	10.7	52.1**	21.4**	70.4**	23.7**
IET7562/Pawanpeer	0.2	2.0	19.0**	1.5	-3.3	31.0**	3.1*	16.3**	34.0**	55.9**
Kanakjeera/IR50	2.2*	6.2**	-1.4	19.6**	-14.9**	18.8**	-15.5**	7.5**	160.4**	50.4**
Kanakjeera/TAU18	3.9**	3.8**	6.4**	6.1	-17.2**	5.2	17.2**	28.6**	33.8**	37.2**
IR50/Pawanpeer	-0.7	7.7**	24.5**	11.6**	22.8**	29.8**	61.3**	44.7**	98.7**	61.1**
IR50/TAU18	-4.1**	-1.5	-15.1**	-3.0*	-1.3	33.7**	-3.2*	5.2**	24.1**	16.3**
Pawanpeer/TAU18	7.3**	6.4**	-5.7**	10.2**	-10.5	13.4*	-0.0	6.2**	35.2**	29.8**
SE	1.3	1.3	1.4	1.5	0.6	0.4	2.4	2.5	1.1	0.8

^a * = significance at P = 5%. ** = significance at P = 1%. HBT = heterobeltiosis, ID = inbreeding depression

Zinc increases rate of twin seedlings of rice

Huang Yiqiang, Tan Zhijun, and Deng Hongde, Hunan Hybrid Rice Research Center, Changsha 410125, China

We studied how Zn affected the rate of twin seedlings in polyembryonic rice varieties: *indica* Shuang 3 and Shuang 13, and *japonica* Lu 52.

Three hundred dehulled seeds per treatment were soaked in different concentrations of Zn²⁺ (ZnSO₄) solution at 37°C for 1 d. The check was soaked in distilled water. The seeds were then sterilized in 0.1% mercuric chloride for 10 min and placed in the same solution at 25°C to hasten germination. Twin seedling rates were calculated 4 d later.